

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Project Report

Interim report/ Final report

Case study: Mixture risk assessment of marine Arctic pollutants: exposure, hazard and risk assessment.

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Abstract

The Case Study aims to evaluate the cumulative risk of chemical mixtures in the Arctic marine environment, where pollutants originate from industrial activities, shipping, oil and gas exploration, and long-range atmospheric transport. Arctic ecosystems face unique challenges due to low temperatures, slow degradation rates, and bioaccumulation of persistent pollutants in food webs. This study integrates the Source-To-Outcome Pathway (STOP) framework, which combines Aggregate Exposure Pathways (AEPs) and Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) to systematically assess the impact of chemical mixtures on Arctic species. The study employs environmental monitoring data, ecotoxicological hazard data with the aim to perform risk assessment to evaluate mixture effects. Key findings indicate that Arctic species are exposed to complex mixtures of metals and organics that may potentially result in mixture risk. The work to date has focused on developing data handling workflows for exposure data from national databases and common (eco)toxicological hazard thresholds, linking these together for mixture risk assessment using exemplified data sets for Arctic pollutants. The study supports regulatory frameworks by developing improved approaches for mixture risk assessment and predictive toxicology models. Future work will refine STOP applications, strengthen engagement with stakeholders, and expand mixture risk assessment methodologies.

Key Words

regulatory relevance, innovative methods, Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA), environmental monitoring, metals, chemical mixtures, mixture risk drivers, Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP), exposure modelling, aggregated exposure, marine, Aggregate Exposure Pathways (AEP), Arctic

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Acronyms

AO - Adverse Outcome

AEP - Aggregate Exposure Pathway

AOP - Adverse Outcome Pathway

API - Application Programming Interface

CA - Concentration Addition

EC_x - Effective Concentration – x%

ERA - (Environmental) Risk Assessment

FAIR - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability

IA - Independent Action

KE - Key Event

MEC - Measured Environmental Concentration

MRA - Mixture Risk Assessment

MIE - Molecular Initiating Event

NGRA - Next Generation Risk Assessment

NOEC - No Observed Effect Concentration

POPs - Persistent Organic Pollutants

QSAR - Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship

RP - Reference Point

RAdb - Risk Assessment Database

RQ - Risk Quotient

SRQ - Sum of Risk Quotients

Glossary

Adverse Outcome (AO) An adverse biological impact that is the ultimate consequence of an Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP).

Aggregate Exposure Pathway (AEP) A comprehensive organization of the routes of exposure for a given organism and stressor, from any relevant sources to receptors. (via Teeguarden et al, 2016)

Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP). AD6.5 A conceptual framework for organizing, synthesizing, and presenting specialized scientific knowledge regarding the linkage (a series of connected Key Events, KEs) between perturbation of a specific biological target, pathway, or process by a stressor (Molecular Initiating Event, MIE), and a consequent Adverse Outcome(s) (AOs) considered relevant to risk assessment, regulatory decision-making, and/or environmental management.

Application Programming Interface (API) An interface to a piece of software (often a server) allowing for resources to be accessed using some manner of programmatic query.

Concentration Addition (CA) A simple model for predicting the effects of multiple stressors by treating each of them as an increase in the concentration of a single stressor. Generally used when stressors share a mode of action (European Commission: Directorate-General for Health and Consumers, *Toxicity and assessment of chemical mixtures*, European Commission, 2012, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2772/21444>).

Effective Concentration - x% (ECx) A Reference Point and Threshold of Toxicological Concern used in ecotoxicology to describe the lowest stressor concentration at which x% of a population experiences adverse effects for a given species and endpoint (European Commission: Directorate-General for Health and Consumers, *Toxicity and assessment of chemical mixtures*, European Commission, 2012, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2772/21444>).

Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) The Fair Data Principles are a set of guidelines designed to maximize the scientific and social value of data by making it as easy to find, access and use as possible. Sometimes used as a verb or noun: *to FAIRify, FAIRification*. (<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>)

Independent Action (IA) A simple model for predicting the effects of multiple stressors by summing their responses. Generally used when stressors have diverse modes of action (European Commission: Directorate-General for Health and Consumers, *Toxicity and assessment of chemical mixtures*, European Commission, 2012, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2772/21444>).

Key Event (KE) Any relevant biological event in an Adverse Outcome Pathway, including the first (Molecular Initiating Event) and last (Adverse Outcome).

Measured Environmental Concentration (MEC) The concentration of a given stressor measured in the environment using analytical chemistry.

Mixture Risk Assessment (MRA) AD6.5 Method of assessing risks to health or the environment posed by multiple substances such as chemicals.

Molecular Initiating Event (MIE) AD6.5 A specialised type of Key Event that represents the initial point of chemical/stressor interaction at the molecular level within the organism that results in a perturbation that starts the AOP (OECD, 2018b)

Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) D2.3 In the context of PARC, NGRA refers to the concept of using data from New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for chemical risk assessment. In its ideal the concept relies on tiered combinations of in silico tools, complex in vitro systems, organ models and omics approaches in conjunction with physiologically based toxicokinetic modelling and complex exposure models. While the concept of NGRA comprises Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and quantitative AOPs as established tools for hazard assessment, it is not limited to these, nor does it exclude the use of in vivo data or histopathology. However, it puts a strong emphasis on using state-of-the-art systems and as such is predominantly mechanism-driven, and not driven by apical (toxicological) endpoints." [1] (Marx-Stoelting P et al., 2022). [1] Marx-Stoelting P. et al. (2022); DOI: 10.1007/s00204-022-03435-7

No Observed Effect Concentration (NOEC) A Reference Point and Threshold of Toxicological Concern used in ecotoxicology to describe the stressor concentration at which statistically significant adverse effects are expected for a given species and endpoint (European Commission: Directorate-General for Health and Consumers, *Toxicity and assessment of chemical mixtures*, European Commission, 2012, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2772/21444>).

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) A grouping of organic pollutants that have been identified as posing a particular risk to the environment due to their toxicity and resistance to biodegradation (<https://www.epa.gov/international-cooperation/persistent-organic-pollutants-global-issue-global-response>).

Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) Quantitative Structure Activity Relationships are models that predict the behavior, fate and properties of a chemical based on those of other chemicals with similar structures (<https://echa.europa.eu/support/registration/how-to-avoid-unnecessary-testing-on-animals/qsar-models>).

Reference Point (RP) (Synonym: POD (Point of Departure)) AD6.5: Defined point on an experimental dose-response relationship for the critical effect (i.e., the biologically relevant effect occurring at the lowest dose level). This term is synonymous to point of departure. Reference points include the lowest or no observed adverse effect level (LOAEL/NOAEL) or benchmark dose lower confidence limit (BDML), used to derive a reference value or Margin of Exposure in human and animal health risk assessment. In the ecological area, these include lethal dose (LD50), effect concentration (EC5/ECx), no (adverse)effect concentration/dose (NOEC/NOAEC/NOAED), and no (adverse) effect level (NEL/NOAEL) (EFSA et al., 2019b).

Risk Assessment Database (Radb) NIVA's Risk Assessment Database, a software tool for conducting environmental risk assessments using exposure and effects data (via <https://www.niva.no/en/radb>).

Risk Quotient (RQ) A simple risk metric, used to quantify the probability and severity of a potential adverse impact on the environment. Calculated by dividing a Predicted or Measured Environmental Concentration (PEC or MEC) of a chemical by its Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC)

Sum of Risk Quotients (SRQ) A simple summation of the Risk Quotients (RQs) of multiple stressors, used to make a rough assessment of the environmental impact posed by a mixture of pollutants to a given environment.

1. Introduction

The Arctic marine environment is increasingly subject to anthropogenic pressures due to climate change, industrial expansion, and global pollutant transport. Chemical pollutants, including persistent organic pollutants (POPs), heavy metals, and industrial contaminants, pose significant ecological risks to Arctic species (AMAP, 2018; Letcher et al., 2010). The Arctic's cold climate and slow degradation processes lead to prolonged persistence of contaminants, facilitating bioaccumulation and biomagnification in marine food webs (Beyer et al., 2014). Traditional regulatory frameworks have primarily focused on single-chemical risk assessments, yet real-world exposure scenarios involve complex chemical mixtures, creating substantial challenges for risk prediction and environmental management (Backhaus & Faust, 2012; Ankley et al., 2010). However, real-world exposures involve mixtures of chemicals that can interact in complex ways, producing additive, synergistic, or antagonistic effects. Regulatory frameworks have not fully incorporated mixture risk assessments, creating challenges in predicting and mitigating the impact of chemical mixtures on Arctic ecosystems.

Regulatory advancements necessitate innovative frameworks to address the complexities of mixture risk assessments (MRA). The Source-To-Outcome Pathway (STOP) framework integrates Aggregate Exposure Pathways (AEPs) and Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) to systematically evaluate the impacts of chemical mixtures in the environment (Teeguarden et al., 2016). The STOP concept aligns with recent advancements in regulatory toxicology, aiming to bridge the gap between chemical exposure and adverse (ecological) effects (Ankley et al., 2010). While AEPs characterize the source, transport, and exposure routes of pollutants to its internal dose at site of toxic action, AOPs provide a mechanistic understanding of biological responses arising from the initial interaction with its molecular target to adverse outcomes at different levels of biological organization (Dorne et al., 2023; Fisher & Fox, 2023).

While classical risk assessment relies on use of environmental no-impact thresholds such as predicted no-effect concentrations, a STOP framework may utilize data that span the AOP continuum, using commonly adopted principles for combined toxicity assessments such as Concentration Addition (CA) and Independent Action (IA). Such approach could involve a tiered approach using Measured (MECs) or Predicted Environmental Concentration (PECs) first towards Predicted No Effect Concentration (PNEC) to derive environmentally-focused risk quotients ($RQ_{\text{environment}}$), and finally to use ecotoxicological base-set data (NOECs, EC_x etc.) for selected species-groups or taxa ($RQ_{\text{species-group}}$) and finally deriving mode-of-action (or AOP) relevant risk quotients (RQ_{AOP}) based on point of departure (PODs) calculations using AOPs as guide to select relevant effects data. Such approach maximizes the utility of existing single-substance assessments, ensuring that further, more detailed MRA is conducted when initial findings indicate a significant environmental risk (Backhaus & Faust, 2012). If substantial discrepancies between CA and IA predictions are detected, mode-of-action-driven analyses can be considered to refine risk estimates.

Risk quotients (RQs) for individual chemicals are calculated as the ratio of the MEC and PECs to the impact thresholds for the environment, species-groups or PODs. Sum of Risk Quotients (SRQ) can be derived by aggregating individual RQs across mixture components, assuming CA or IA as principles for combined toxicity. If the SRQ exceeds 1, it suggests that the chemicals in the mixture pose a risk, even if individual chemical RQs remain below the risk threshold. The magnitude and frequency of RQ and SRQ exceedance of risk threshold (SRQ>1 and RQ>1) can be used to characterize the persistence and severity of potential environmental impact.

To enhance the robustness of risk characterization, a combined deterministic and probabilistic risk assessment approach can be applied. Deterministic assessments use fixed values for MEC/PEC (i.e. percentiles, median or similar) in relation to impact thresholds to provide conservative, worst-case scenario estimate, while probabilistic assessments incorporate variability and uncertainty by using statistical distributions of exposure and effect data. This allows for the calculation of exceedance probabilities, offering a more refined understanding of the likelihood and extent of risks. A combination of these approaches can be used, especially when exposure and effects data are well supported by data, whereas data-gap filling approaches can be performed using model predictions for exposure (e.g. by AEP-informed multimedia modeling) or effects (e.g. QSAR models).

2. Aim

This case study aims to develop and implement a framework for MRA of chemical mixtures in Arctic marine environments. By integrating spatio-temporal exposure data, hazard (no-impact) thresholds, and computational toxicology, the case study seeks to characterize mixture toxicity, identify key risk drivers, and establish a tiered assessment approach that can be incorporated into a STOP framework, including a web-based visualization tools based on the STOP.

Key objectives include:

- Developing a computational platform for MRA with a focus on mixture toxicity from arctic pollutants.
- Identifying priority pollutants and risk drivers using Norwegian Environmental Monitoring data.
- Assessing spatial and temporal trends in mixture heterogeneity and predicting ecological impacts on Arctic species.
- Implementing mixture risk assessment methodologies based on CA and IA.
- Enhancing risk characterization through a combination of deterministic and probabilistic approaches.
- Disseminating findings via scientific publications and engagement with regulatory stakeholders.

Development of integrated tools for STOP predictions (WP8.3) will be performed in parallel with establishing data libraries for exposure and effect information (WP7.2). The case study will use existing spatio-temporal data for chemical presence in the marine Arctic environment of Norway, available effects data to marine (and/or aquatic species) to perform mixture risk assessment, identify the most relevant risk drivers and propose a tiered approach to computationally and experimentally assess potential impact on selected marine organisms in the Arctic. The project aims to apply silico and use experimental toxicity data from marine species to predict environmental impacts of existing and emerging pollutants, with a focus on Arctic species and Arctic-relevant chemical mixtures. The work presented herein focuses on demonstrating workflows for exposure and hazard assessment, and how these can be integrated into a STOP-informed risk assessment and associated web-based dashboards.

3. Methods

This study integrates computational approaches to assess exposure and effects as basis for risk assessment. The methodology consists of the following components:

3.1 Environmental Monitoring

Data on legacy and emerging pollutants were captured from the national chemical monitoring database Vanmiljø (<https://vanmiljo.miljodirektoratet.no/>), open literature, and NIVA's Risk Assessment Database (RAdb) to identify prevalent Arctic pollutants. A common data conversion pipeline (Figure 1) was developed in R to facilitate environmental exposure data extraction to a FAIR, standardized format and import to RAdb. The effort has been a joint venture with PARC P7.2.2's Chemicals in the environment metadata schema. The pipeline was subsequently used to convert 30+ years of aquatic monitoring data for Arctic regions.

Figure 1: Workflow for accessing data from the *Vannmiljø* server. Monitoring data (and supplementary geographical data from *Geonorge*, Norway's mapping service), are downloaded via API call based on a specific query (stressors of interest, area, time period, etc.). Data were then curated and transformed to a common metadata schema and using code lists commonly adopted in PARC T7.2.2 "Chemicals in the environment" project prior to import into the data repository of NIVA RAdB. Exposure data can then be plotted, analyzed, and used in risk assessments using a standardized format supported by controlled vocabularies and available ontologies.

3.2 Hazard assessment

Environmental hazard data was curated and integrated into a reproducible R-based standardization workflow from major public sources to compile PNECs, ECx and NOECs and similar toxicity thresholds for no-environmental impact (e.g. reference points) for Arctic relevant chemicals, species and habitats. Key databases used include ENVIROTOX (Connors et al., 2019; Health and Environmental Sciences Institute (HESI), 2021), NORMAN Ecotoxicology Database (Dulio et al., 2020; NORMAN Association, 2024), and USEPA ECOTOX (Olker et al., 2022). These data sets were accessed via APIs, database dumps or flat-file data structures and curated for hazard assessment. The curation involved structured workflows built on principles proposed by Spilsbury et al. (2024), applying documented filtering steps (Spilsbury, 2023), harmonization of units and terminology, excluding incomplete records and missing data, and harmonizing metadata and data formats to streamline data for further use (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Conceptual workflow for import/access, curation and filtering of data from major public sources of environmental hazard data. Controlled vocabularies used for study design and effect reporting parameters were collected and harmonized using RAdb. Comptox is used as a source for physical and chemical properties like molecular weights. After filtering, thresholds of toxicity and key study design parameters are summarized in a harmonized format.

3.3 Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP)

The AOP concept is at the core of our approach to mixture risk assessment as it facilitates grouping Arctic pollutants according to their most important MOA. Although several AOPs may be relevant for Arctic pollutants, two AOP networks were developed as they are particularly relevant to a broad suite of Arctic pollutants and species. Building on published key event relationships (KER), the AOP networks specifically focus on the molecular initiating event (MIE) of ROS formation, which is – through a series of key events (KE) – lead to reduced growth as the final adverse outcome (AO) (figure 3).

2Figure 3: Schematic presentation of an arctic relevant AOP network for explaining the causal relationship between ROS production and the chronic endpoint growth decreases. Event identifiers from AOPwiki (<https://aopwiki.org/events>).

3.4 Risk assessment

Risk quotients were calculated on the basis of the MEC and PEC (predicted as 1/3rd of the Level of Quantitation (LOQ) or 1/10th of the Level of Detection (LOQ)), and chemical-specific RQ-values determined by eq. 1. Mixture risk was calculated as sum of risk quotients (SRQ) using eq. 2.

$$\text{Risk Quotient (RQ)} = \text{exposure concentration} / \text{predicted no-impact concentration (PNEC, NOEC or POD)} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$\text{Sum of Risk quotients (SRQ)} = \sum(\text{exposure concentration} / \text{predicted no-impact concentration (PNEC, NOEC or POD)}) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

To integrate monitoring data and chemical hazard information, NIVA's Risk Assessment Database (RAdb) was used, facilitating standardization of exposure and effects data handling.

3.5 Integration and Visualization tools

Basic functional prototypes of data visualization dashboards were developed to represent the exposure, hazard and risk assessment modules that comprise an integrated STOP model (see T8.3 for more details, Figure 6). A prototype inspection and exploratory data analysis module was constructed specifically to allow for quality checking and aggregation of exposure data prior to environmental risk assessment (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Prototype exploratory data analysis dashboard. Here, exposure data can be reviewed across a variety of factors (environmental compartment, temporal and spatial variation, data homogeneity, etc.) before being used for environmental risk assessment.

4. Results

The case study has largely focused on developing data handling practices and developing harmonized solutions for importing, standardizing data, and visualization in standalone analysis steps and dashboards. Although the case study addresses both inorganic (metals) and organic chemicals in the Arctic, particular attention has been given copper to develop, test and demonstrate approaches and tools.

4.1. Exposure assessment

Figure 53: Leaflet map of environmental monitoring data for 2023 from the Vannmiljø database. Filtered to sampling sites above 66.5 degrees North and colored by pollutant group.

Monitoring data were mapped (Figure 5) and analyzed by relevant environmental compartments, stressor (pollutant) types (Figure 6). Legacy organic and heavy metal stressors have been prioritized for long-term monitoring by the Norwegian government, while a range of PFAS have more recently been added to lists of concern. Of the heavy metals, copper has been identified as one of the stressors with highest relevance to Arctic pollution, due to its widespread use as a biocide in aquaculture and shipping (Weber, F., Esmaili, N., 2023), as well as its potency and exposure potential for several Arctic species. Consequently, it was decided to use copper as a *prima inter pares* model stressor for workflow development and exposure assessment.

Figure 6: Heatmap of environmental monitoring data for 2023 from the Vannmiljø database, highlighting the diversity of pollutants monitoring in different environmental compartments. Particular focus will be given assessments of pollutants in the coastal zone as this is expected to areas being impacted to the largest degree.

4.2. Hazard assessment

In this case study curated hazard data for copper (Figure 74) are used to assess and predict chemical risk in Arctic environments. Even though hazard data for copper is generally abundantly available from public sources with both acute and chronic effects assessed in many aquatic species representing several layers of the food-web, data is sparse for Arctic species. Therefore, species to species extrapolation from similar temperate species tested under temperate conditions is key to derive NOECs and PNECs. Generally, several types of data are relevant to deriving appropriate extrapolation factors, but as a first line of evidence we are using hazard threshold data from public sources. Figure 7 summarises toxicity thresholds from studies reported in ECOTOX at a sufficient level of detail. Key trophic layers are covered by tests in several species. This will allow us to estimate the magnitude of inter-species difference within each trophic layer.

Figure 74: Violin plot of hazard thresholds [μM] for adverse outcomes (AO)/apical endpoints and other endpoints potentially relevant as molecular initiating events (MIE) or other key events (KE) available from ECOTOX knowledgebase for biota exposed to copper. Reported thresholds are categorized as no-effect concentrations (<10% departure from control levels, e.g. NOEL), low effect concentrations (10% \leq departure from control levels < 50%, e.g., EC10), or high effect concentrations (50% \leq departure from control levels, e.g., EC50). Study type classification (acute/chronic) is based on test type reporting in ECOTOX or – for studies where this classification is missing – based on reported exposure durations.

4.3. Risk assessment

As work until now has been devoted development of data handling workflows, curation of exposure and effects data, risk assessment has not yet been performed on relevant Arctic mixtures and will be the subject of future work. It is envisioned, however, that MRA using RQ and SRQ approaches for the environment using PNECs, species groups (using NOEC and EC_x data) and AOP-informed approaches (e.g. mechanistically informed data) will be initial steps in this work and undertaken in the REMIX project. One of the main goals of the future work will be to consolidate the different analysis workflows for subsequent integration into a STOP model infrastructure as part of work in WP8.3. The data generated will be made available through a dedicated web-based dashboard, the STOPredictor (Fig. 8). This dashboard will work as a one-stop facility for performing case study-specific exposure assessment, hazard characterization and risk assessment for single chemicals and mixtures of these in the current case study.

Figure 8: Prototype of the STOPredictor dashboard for visualization of case study-specific data for exposure, spatio-temporal risk and risk drivers

5. Discussion

This study highlights the development of data handling workflows for exposure and hazard data, as well as their integration into a MRA model infrastructure (STOP). The STOP and its associated dashboard, STOPredictor, are designed to provide a flexible, case study-specific modeling and prediction toolbox. It enables semi-automated risk assessment, reducing the time and resources required to harmonize heterogeneous data from diverse sources.

The STOP framework also aims to offer a structured, mechanism-based approach for MRA. It utilizes exposure data to develop risk metrics based on well-established risk assessment principles, such as Risk Quotients (RQs) and Sum of Risk Quotients (SRQs) with different protective goals in mind. By applying different thresholds as the basis for risk predictions, the framework can support a tiered approach that improves predictive accuracy progressively using:

- Predicted No-Effect Concentrations (PNECs) as reference points for environmental risk,
- No-Observed-Effect Concentrations (NOECs) for species-specific risk, and
- Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP)-informed Points of Departure (PODs) for mechanistically focused assessments.

The latter is proposed as a cornerstone in the development of Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) by incorporating a broader array of data, including New Approach Methodologies (NAMs).

Current efforts have focused on developing standardized workflows for handling exposure and effects data, as well as prototyping visualization tools to display exposure, hazard, and risk predictions. These tools follow CA as a guiding principle for assessing combined toxicity. Additionally, this initiative is linked to the development of standardized data reporting formats (DRFs) and dashboard to FAIRify environmental exposure and dose-response data within the scope of PARC WP7.2.

This case study specifically addresses the MRA of Arctic marine pollutants, focusing on eco-relevant mixtures. A single model pollutant (copper) has been selected as a pragmatic solution for developing and refining the

workflows in the initial phase of the work. As the case study will continue within the remit of the REMIX project, future efforts will be focused on consolidating the current workflows and expand these to addressing more complex exposure scenarios involving spatial and temporal exposure trends.

5.1. Method development – validation maturity

Current work has mainly focused on developing workflows that can import, standardize and use exposure and effect data for larger scale implementation into risk assessment of single chemicals and mixtures. As such, its integration is still conceptual in nature, although development of individual workflows and model infrastructure is in progress.

5.2. Regulatory relevance

The principles and methodologies for exposure, hazard, and risk assessments are well established within the scientific community. However, large-scale implementation of these approaches into regulatory decision-making remains a challenge. The integration of modeling infrastructure such as the STOP aims to enhance the regulatory applicability of MRA in environmental contexts, particularly for Arctic pollutants where little has been done up to date.

5.3. Additional research needs

As the methodologies for exposure and hazard assessment continue to develop within WP6 and other related work packages, several research needs have been identified to enhance the robustness of the STOP. The following areas require further research to refine predictive models, fill critical data gaps, and ensure comprehensive MRA for Arctic pollutants.

- **Enhanced spatio-temporal monitoring of Arctic pollutants:** Long-term environmental datasets are essential to track pollutant trends, assess mixture exposures, and validate risk models. Arctic chemical monitoring data centers around a few groups of chemicals (metals, PAHs, PFAS) and could benefit with larger diversity to ensure that MRA are accounting for realistic mixtures and risk drivers.
- **Expanded ecotoxicological data for Arctic species:** Current datasets predominantly focus on temperate species, requiring species-to-species extrapolation for Arctic ecosystems. Efforts to develop such extrapolations would enable filling some of the knowledge gaps existing and support mixture risk assessment.
- **Integration of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs):** The transition towards Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) requires regulatory acceptance of predictive toxicology approaches, including Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP)-based assessments and computational exposure modeling.
- **Adoption of Common Data Standards:** The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles facilitate data sharing, improving the availability and reliability of exposure and hazard datasets. Availability of common approaches for controlled vocabularies, standardized ontologies and terminologies for metadata and data reporting is required to take larger advantage of the data available for MRA.
- **Development of Tiered Assessment Strategies:** A tiered and semi-automated approach such as STOP, would enable progressive refinement of risk predictions using different no-impact thresholds (PNEC, NOEC and AOP-informed values). Further enhancement would include inclusion of probabilistic risk assessment in the STOP to account for variance in underlying data and uncertainty propagated from exposure and hazard assessments.

6. Conclusion

The Case Study demonstrates the feasibility of integrating exposure modeling, predictive toxicology, with a potential to advance environmental MRA. While still in development, the concept of risk assessment of single chemicals and mixtures used in the STOP builds upon well-established scientific principles that can be expanded to

support more mechanistically-informed approaches. Future work will focus on maturing the individual workflows of the STOP, demonstrate utility using Arctic pollutants, present and discuss principles and approaches with different stakeholders.

7. Information for the Data management

Exposure and hazard data collected from different sources have been standardized for the purpose of performing risk assessment and stored in NIVA's Risk Assessment Database (RAdb) for further use. These data will be made publicly available in accordance with FAIR data principles through repositories such as Zenodo or the PARC data hub whenever feasible.

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